

SOME CHARACTERIZATIONS OF AUTOMORPHISMS OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL SPIN FACTOR

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Abstract. *In the present paper, we investigate 2-local linear operators on vector spaces. Sufficient conditions are obtained for the linearity of a 2-local linear operator on a finite-dimensional vector space. Based on these results we describe 2-local derivations and automorphisms on low-dimension Jordan algebras. Also, we develop methods of construction of 2-local linear operators which are not linear operators. Applying these methods we investigate low-dimension automorphism of three dimensional spin factor.*

Keywords: *automorphisms, Jordan algebras, linear operators, local automorphism, spin factor.*

In 1997, P. Semrl introduced and investigated so-called 2-local derivations and 2-local automorphisms on operator algebras. He described such maps on the algebra $B(H)$ of all bounded linear operators on an infinite-dimensional separable Hilbert space H . Namely, he proved that every 2-local derivation (automorphism) on $B(H)$ is a derivation (respectively an automorphism).

A similar description of 2-local derivations for the finite-dimensional case appeared later in the work of S. Kim and J. Kim. In the paper of Y. Lin and T. Wong 2-local derivations have been described on matrix algebras over finite-dimensional division rings. Sh. Ayupov and K. Kudaybergenov suggested a new technique and have generalized the above-mentioned results mentioned above for arbitrary Hilbert spaces. Namely, they proved that every 2-local derivation on the algebra $B(H)$ of all linear bounded operators on an arbitrary Hilbert space H is a derivation.

A similar result is obtained for automorphisms by them. Sh. Ayupov, K. Kudaybergenov and F. Arzikulov extended the above results for 2-local derivations and gave a proof of the theorem for arbitrary von Neumann algebras.

M.J. Burgos, F.J. Fernandez Polo, J.J. Garces and A.M. Peralta established that every 2-local $*$ -homomorphism from a von Neumann algebra into a C^* -algebra is a linear $*$ -homomorphism. These authors also proved that every 2-local Jordan $*$ -homomorphism from a JBW^* -algebra into a JB_* -algebra is a Jordan $*$ -homomorphism. Later, Sh. Ayupov and K. Kudaybergenov prove that any 2-local automorphism on an arbitrary AW^* -algebra without finite type I direct summands is an automorphism. Sh. Ayupov and K. Kudaybergenov also proved that every 2-local automorphism on a finite-dimensional semi-simple Lie algebra over an algebraically closed field of characteristic zero is an automorphism and showed that each finite-dimensional nilpotent Lie algebra with dimension ≥ 2 admits a 2-local automorphism which is not an automorphism.

The present paper is devoted to automorphisms and 2-local automorphisms on Jordan algebras.

Sh. Ayupov, F. Arzikulov, N. Umrzaqov and O. Nuriddinov proved that every 2-local 1-automorphism (i.e. implemented by single symmetries) on a finite-dimensional semi-simple Jordan algebra over an algebraically closed field of characteristics different from 2 is an automorphism.

In the present paper, we investigate 2-local automorphisms on low-dimensional Jordan algebras. Namely, we describe automorphisms and 2-local automorphisms on three-dimensional spin factor.

This section is devoted to the description of 2-local automorphisms of indecomposable two and three dimensional Jordan algebras

Let J be a Jordan algebra. Recall that a map $\Delta : J \rightarrow J$ is called a 2-local automorphism, if for any two elements $x, y \in J$ there exists an automorphism $\Phi_{x,y} : J \rightarrow J$ such that $\Delta(x) = \Phi_{x,y}(x)$, $\Delta(y) = \Phi_{x,y}(y)$

Note that, if a 2-local automorphism Δ of a finite-dimensional Jordan algebra J is linear and the determinant of its matrix is not equal to zero (i.e., Δ is surjective), then it is an automorphism. Indeed, applying the definition of 2-local automorphism to the elements $x, x^2 \in J$ we obtain that Δ is a Jordan automorphism, i.e., $\Delta(x^2) = \Delta(x)\Delta(x)$, $x \in J$.

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(xy) &= \Delta((x+y)^2 - x^2 - y^2) = \Delta((x+y)^2 - \Delta(x)^2 - \Delta(y)^2) = \\ &= \Delta(x+y)\Delta(x+y) - \Delta(x)\Delta(x) - \Delta(y)\Delta(y) = \Delta(x)\Delta(y) \end{aligned}$$

for any $x, y \in J$

Let J_5 be a Jordan algebra with the following table multiplication

$$e_1^2 = e_1 \quad e_2^2 = e_2 \quad e_3^2 = e_1 + e_2 \quad e_1e_2 = 0 \quad e_1e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3 \quad e_2e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3$$

i.e., three-dimensional spin factor.

Theorem 1.1. *A linear operator φ on J_5 is an automorphism if and only if the matrix generating φ is equal to one of the following matrix*

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \pm 1 \end{pmatrix}, & A_2 &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \mp 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \pm 1 \\ \pm \frac{1}{2} & \mp \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ A_3 &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \mp 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \pm 1 \\ \mp \frac{1}{2} & \pm \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & A_4 &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \pm 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1.2. *Every local automorphism on J_5 is an automorphism.*

Theorem 1.3. *Every 2-local automorphism on J_5 is an automorphism.*

REFERENCES

1. Larson D. R., Sourour A. R. Local derivations and local automorphisms of $B(X)$. Proc. Sympos. Pure Math., Providence, Rhode Island Part 2, 1990. Vol. 51. P. 187{194. URI: <http://hdl.handle.net/1828/2373>

2. R.Kadison. Local derivations, J.Algebra, 130(1990), 494-509. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-8693\(90\)90095-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-8693(90)90095-6).
3. I.Kashuba, M.E.Martin, Deformations of Jordan algebras of dimension four, Journal of Algebra 399, 288-289 (2014).
4. B.Johnson, Local derivations on C^* - algebras are derivations, Trans. Amer. Math, Soc., 353 (2001), 313-325. DOI: 10.2307/221975